

Adversarial Vulnerability and Defense in Human Detection: An Experimental Study Using FGSM, PGD, and Adversarial Training on the HERIDAL Dataset

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Abstract Adversarial attacks pose a serious threat to the reliability of modern artificial intelligence systems, especially in computer vision. Although such attacks rely on very small, often imperceptible perturbations of the input data, they can cause a dramatic degradation of deep neural network performance. This paper investigates the vulnerability of an object detection model to adversarial attacks and evaluates the effectiveness of adversarial training as a defense mechanism. The YOLOv8 model, trained for human detection in images, is used as the target model. The Fast Gradient Sign Method (FGSM) and Projected Gradient Descent (PGD) are implemented as adversarial attacks using multiple perturbation parameters. Model performance is evaluated using global metrics, per-image analysis, and detailed error analysis. The results show that FGSM attacks lead to a significant performance drop, primarily due to increased missed detections. The application of adversarial training substantially improves model robustness, although complete immunity to strong attacks is not achieved. These findings highlight the importance of systematic security evaluation of AI models before their deployment in real-world systems.	Article history Received: 30.3.2026. Revised: 29.4.2026. Accepted: 11.5.2026. Keywords Adversarial AI, FGSM, YOLOv8, Object Detection, Adversarial Training.
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1 Introduction

Deep neural networks have achieved remarkable performance across a wide range of computer vision tasks, including object detection, image classification, and visual tracking. Their deployment in safety-critical systems such as surveillance infrastructure, autonomous vehicles, and medical imaging has grown substantially in recent years. However, alongside these advances, a fundamental vulnerability has been identified. Deep learning models are susceptible to adversarial examples - inputs that have been deliberately modified with small, carefully crafted perturbations designed to cause incorrect model outputs [1].

Unlike natural image corruptions such as noise or blur, adversarial perturbations are optimized to exploit the internal decision boundaries of neural networks.

Although these modifications are typically imperceptible to human observers, they can cause dramatic degradation in model performance [1], [2]. This disconnect between human perception and machine-learning behavior poses serious risks in real-world deployments, where undetected failures may have significant safety or security consequences.

The objective of this work is to experimentally investigate this vulnerability and evaluate the effectiveness of adversarial training as a defense mechanism. Specifically, the study demonstrates FGSM attacks across multiple perturbation strengths, quantifies their impact using standard detection metrics (mAP50, mAP50-95, Precision, and Recall), and analyzes the degree to which adversarial training improves model robustness. All conclusions are supported by numerical metrics, graphical results, and visual examples.

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2 Background and Theoretical Foundations

2.1 What are adversarial attacks?

Adversarial attacks are intentional manipulations of input data designed to cause a machine learning model to produce incorrect or misleading outputs. These attacks introduce small, carefully crafted perturbations that exploit vulnerabilities in the model's decision boundaries. Although such perturbations are often imperceptible to human observers, they can significantly degrade model robustness. Adversarial attacks highlight the lack of inherent robustness in deep neural networks, especially in safety and security-critical applications [2], [3].

2.2 Adversarial Examples in Deep Learning

Deep learning models have achieved great performance in a wide range of computer vision tasks, including image classification, object detection, and visual tracking [5]. Their success is mainly attributed to the ability to automatically learn complicated feature representations from large amounts of data. Despite these advances, it has become increasingly evident that such models are not inherently robust and can be vulnerable to malicious inputs.

Adversarial examples are among the most prominent manifestations of this vulnerability [4]. An adversarial example is an input that has been intentionally modified with a small disruption designed to mislead a trained model. These changes are usually constrained to be very small under a chosen norm, making them difficult or even impossible to detect by visual inspection. Their impact on the model's output can be substantial.

The existence of adversarial examples highlights a fundamental mismatch between human perception and the way deep neural networks process information. Humans often focus on semantic content, whereas neural networks rely on learned numerical patterns in high-dimensional input spaces. As a result, small, structured changes to the input can significantly alter internal feature activations and shift the input across a decision boundary without producing perceptible visual changes [4].

From a practical standpoint, this vulnerability poses serious concerns. In applications such as surveillance systems, autonomous navigation, and safety monitoring, the inability to detect objects that are clearly present in the environment may lead to severe and potentially irreversible failures. Adversarial examples are not merely a theoretical curiosity, but a real-world threat that must be systematically studied and addressed.

2.3 Fast Gradient Sign Method (FGSM)

Among the adversarial attack techniques, the Fast Gradient Sign Method is commonly used as a baseline approach for evaluating model robustness [2]. FGSM exploits the gradient of the loss function with respect to the input to determine the direction in which the input should be perturbed to increase the prediction error. The perturbation is applied directly to the input data and scaled by a parameter ϵ , which controls the attack strength. Even for small values of ϵ , FGSM can significantly degrade model performance, despite the perturbations remaining visually imperceptible [6].

The generation of an adversarial example using FGSM can be expressed as [7]:

$$x_{adv} = x + \epsilon \cdot \text{sign}(\nabla_x L) \quad \text{Eq 1}$$

... where x is the original input, L is the loss function, and epsilon ϵ controls the strength of the attack.

2.4 Object Detection and YOLO Architecture

Object detection is a more complex task than image classification, as it requires the simultaneous identification and localization of multiple objects within a single image. This dual requirement makes detection models especially sensitive to changes that affect spatial features and contextual relationships.

The YOLO (You Only Look Once) family of models addresses object detection by formulating it as a single regression problem [8]. Instead of relying on multiple processing stages, YOLO predicts bounding boxes and class probabilities in a single forward pass of the network. This design enables high inference speed, making YOLO models suitable for real-time applications.

YOLOv8 is a modern iteration of this architecture, incorporating improvements in feature extraction and optimization while maintaining efficiency [9]. The tight coupling between feature extraction and prediction means that changes introduced at the input level can propagate through the network, simultaneously affecting both classification confidence and localization accuracy.

Given its widespread adoption in real-world systems, YOLOv8 provides a realistic and relevant target for studying adversarial robustness. Understanding how adversarial attacks affect such models is important for assessing their reliability in real-world deployments.

2.5 Evaluation Metrics in Object Detection

To meaningfully assess the impact of adversarial attacks, it is necessary to carefully interpret the evaluation metrics used in object detection. Unlike simple accuracy measures, detection metrics provide an explanation of different types of model errors.

mAP50 (mean Average Precision at IoU=0.5) measures the average detection precision at an Intersection over Union (IoU) threshold of 0.5. This metric provides a clear indication of the model's ability to correctly localize and classify objects [10].

mAP50-95 is a more stringent metric that averages precision over multiple IoU thresholds ranging from 0.5 to 0.95. It offers a more comprehensive assessment of detection quality, especially with respect to bounding box localization accuracy [10].

Precision is the ratio of correctly predicted detections to the total number of predicted detections. High precision indicates a low number of false positives.

Recall measures the ratio of correctly detected objects to the total number of ground-truth objects present in the image. This metric is especially important in security-critical applications, as low recall implies that real objects are being missed [2].

In addition to global metrics, an analysis of true positives (TP), false positives (FP), and false negatives (FN) was performed on a per-image basis, allowing for a deeper understanding of the types of errors introduced by adversarial attacks.

These metrics form the basis for the experimental evaluation presented in the following sections.

3 Experimental Setup

3.1 Model Description

The experimental evaluation in this study is performed using the YOLOv8 object detection model [9]. A lightweight variant of the model was selected to enable efficient execution on standard hardware while maintaining sufficient detection capability. The model was trained to perform single-class human detection, which simplifies the analysis and allows the impact of adversarial attack to be studied in a controlled manner.

The choice of a real-time detection model reflects practical deployment scenarios, where efficiency and responsiveness are important. At the same time, such models must maintain reliable performance under non-ideal conditions, including adversarial interference.

3.2 Dataset Description

The experimental evaluation was performed on the HERIDAL (Human detection from imagery in difficult visual environments) dataset, consisting of 1677 images containing human instances annotated with bounding boxes. Humans were treated as a single object class [11]. This design choice simplifies the detection task and enables a more focused analysis of how adversarial changes affect the model's ability to detect object presence, rather than class discrimination.

The dataset reflects a wide range of real-world visual conditions. It includes images with both single and multiple individuals, substantial variations in scale and body pose, partial occlusions, and diverse background environments. Such variability closely resembles realistic deployment scenarios and ensures that the evaluation is not limited to idealized or overly simplified cases. Consequently, the dataset is suitable for assessing both baseline detection performance and robustness under adversarial influence.

To ensure a structured and unbiased evaluation protocol, the dataset was divided into three non-overlapping subsets, as follows:

- 70% training set, used for model learning;
- 20% validation set, used for hyperparameter tuning and model selection;
- 10% test set, used exclusively for final performance evaluation.

The split was performed at the image level to avoid data leakage between subsets and to ensure that no visual overlap exists between training and evaluation data. This separation is important in adversarial settings, where even subtle correlations between datasets could bias robustness estimates.

Importantly, no additional data augmentation techniques were applied during training. This decision was made to maintain a controlled experimental environment, allowing any observed changes in model performance to be attributed directly to the applied adversarial perturbations rather than to implicit robustness introduced through augmentation strategies.

3.3 Attack Implementation

Adversarial attacks were implemented using the Fast Gradient Sign Method (FGSM) [2]. For each input image, the gradient of the loss function with respect to the input was computed, and an adversarial perturbation was generated by applying the signed gradient scaled by the perturbation parameter ϵ .

Multiple values of ϵ were considered in order to systematically evaluate the effect of increasing perturbation strength on detection. Smaller values of ϵ correspond to subtle, visually imperceptible perturbations, while larger values introduce progressively stronger distortions. This range of perturbation magnitudes enables a comprehensive analysis of model vulnerability under both weak and strong adversarial conditions.

Figure 1 Original dataset picture (format: 640×640), used for model training

Figure 2 Adversarially attacked image with FGSM ($\epsilon = 0.03$)

The perturbations were applied directly to the input images, without additional post-processing. This approach ensures that the observed performance degradation is a direct consequence of the FGSM attack itself and not influenced by secondary processing effects.

Despite their visual similarity, the adversarial image contains subtle perturbations that are barely noticeable to humans but significantly impact model predictions. As shown in Figures 1 and 2, changes in the image are almost undetectable to the human eye.

3.4 Adversarial Training Strategy

To evaluate a defense mechanism against FGSM-based adversarial attacks, adversarial training was employed. The original training set of 1174 images (70% of the full HERIDAL dataset) was augmented with adversarially perturbed examples. The augmented dataset was composed of 70% clean images (822 samples) and 30% adversarially perturbed images (352 samples), with all perturbations generated using FGSM at $\epsilon=0.02$. This perturbation level was selected to represent a moderate attack strength, strong enough to meaningfully challenge the model, yet within a range where the visual content of the image remains largely intact. The adversarial examples were generated from randomly selected clean training images.

Adversarial examples were generated offline prior to training using the same gradient-based procedure described in Section 3.3, and no additional perturbation was applied during the forward pass at training time. The model was retrained from scratch using this augmented dataset, with identical hyperparameter settings to the baseline model, to ensure that any observed performance differences are attributable solely to the composition of the training data rather than to differences in optimization.

The resulting adversarially trained model is therefore expected to exhibit improved robustness under adversarial conditions [4], [6], [13], [14].

4 Evaluation of the Model Without Defense

This section presents the experimental evaluation of the baseline YOLOv8 model without any adversarial defense mechanisms. The objective is to establish a reference point for the model under normal conditions and to analyze the impact of FGSM attacks of varying strengths.

4.1 Baseline Performance on Clean Images

The baseline evaluation was performed on the clean test dataset without any adversarial perturbations. Under these conditions, the YOLOv8 model demonstrates stable, reliable performance across all evaluated metrics. The obtained global metrics indicate a good balance between detection accuracy and robustness. The values of mAP50, Precision, and Recall confirm that the model can detect humans across a wide range of scenes, including images with multiple individuals and varying levels of difficulty.

Table 1 Global Results Summary

mAP50	mAP50-95	Precision	Recall
0.5333	0.1875	0.6045	0.492

As shown in Table 1, the achieved mAP50 of 0.5333 indicates that the model can correctly detect and localize humans at the standard IoU threshold, demonstrating satisfactory baseline robustness. This level of performance is consistent with expectations for single-class human detection tasks in real-world visual environments.

The more restrictive mAP50-95 score of 0.1875 reflects the increased strictness of this metric, which averages detection precision across higher IoU thresholds, thereby placing greater emphasis on precise bounding box localization. Lower values of this metric are most often observed in complex scenes involving occlusions, scale variations, and background clutter.

The Precision value of 0.6045 suggests that the model maintains a relatively low rate of false-positive detections, indicating reliable discrimination between human and non-human regions. In contrast, the Recall score of 0.492 indicates that approximately half of the ground-truth human instances are successfully detected, highlighting the trade-off between detection completeness and false-positive reduction.

Overall, these baseline results confirm that the model is properly trained and provide a stable and valid reference for analyzing performance degradation under adversarial attack conditions.

4.2 Global Impact of FGSM Attacks

To evaluate the vulnerability of the model, FGSM attacks were applied using increasing values of the perturbation parameter ϵ . A clear and non-linear degradation is observed as ϵ increases.

Table 2 Detection performance under FGSM attacks

ϵ	mAP50	mAP50-95	Precision	Recall
clean	0.5333	0.1875	0.6045	0.492
0.005	0.3888	0.1305	0.5169	0.3793
0.01	0.255	0.0878	0.4185	0.2874
0.02	0.123	0.0395	0.1892	0.2107
0.03	0.1044	0.033	0.2293	0.1533
0.05	0.0759	0.0214	0.2027	0.1264
0.10	0.0345	0.0085	0.1508	0.069

The results show a steady drop in all metrics as ϵ increases, small changes cause large drops in performance (Table 2).

The mAP50 score drops from 0.5333 to 0.0345, indicating a significant loss in detection accuracy. The mAP50-95 metric follows the same pattern, meaning that bounding box localization also degrades quickly.

Recall shows the sharpest decline. It drops from 0.492 to 0.0690. This means the model misses most of the true objects (humans) as the attack becomes stronger.

Precision decreases slowly, the model becomes more conservative, and it avoids making predictions. This suggests that the model does not produce many false detections initially. As ϵ grows, false positives increase, and precision also drops.

At low-magnitude FGSM adversarial perturbation ($\epsilon=0.005$), the model still works but shows clear weakness. At medium levels ($\epsilon=0.01$ and 0.02), both detection and localizations degrade strongly. The results obtained for higher values of ϵ are showing that model becomes unstable and unreliable, the detector is almost unusable. This confirms that the YOLOv8 model has limited robustness to FGSM attacks, underscoring the need for defense methods that improve stability under adversarial noise.

The most significant decline is visible in the mAP50 and Recall metrics, while Precision decreases more gradually. This behavior indicates that FGSM attacks usually cause the model to miss real objects rather than producing a large number of false detections.

4.3 Per-Image Analysis Under FGSM Attacks

To better understand model behavior under adversarial conditions, we compared the number of people in each image with the detector's predictions. On clean images, predictions are closer to the ground-truth number of humans, whereas FGSM-perturbed images show a clear mismatch, with the model missing people, especially in crowded scenes (Figure 3).

This analysis confirms that FGSM attacks do not cause the model to hallucinate objects, but rather render it partially blind to objects that are actually present.

4.4 Error Distribution Analysis

A detailed analysis of true positives (TP), false positives (FP), and false negatives (FN) provides further understanding of the performance degradation observed under FGSM attacks.

Figure 3 Per-image ground-truth versus prediction under FGSM perturbations

Figure 4 False Negatives, False Positives, True Positives versus ϵ

As shown in Figure 4, the number of false negatives increases rapidly with increasing perturbation magnitude ϵ , indicating that an increasing number of humans are missed by the detector. This behavior directly explains the observed decline in recall.

In contrast, the number of false positives increases at a much slower rate, suggesting that adversarial perturbations do not usually lead to spurious detections. Instead, the number of true positives decreases significantly, reflecting the model's reduced detection capability in the presence of adversarial noise.

Overall, these results confirm that the dominant failure mode under FGSM attacks is the loss of correct detections rather than an increase in incorrect detections.

5 Defense Technique: Adversarial Training

This section evaluates adversarial training as a defense mechanism against FGSM-based adversarial attacks, focusing on its impact on both baseline detection performance and robustness under increasing perturbation strength.

5.1 Baseline Performance After Adversarial Training

To determine how the defense affected baseline performance, the adversarially trained model was first tested.

Table 3 summarizes the slight decrease in clean data performance when compared to the undefended model.

Table 3 Global performance of the adversarially trained model on clean images

mAP50	mAP50-95	Precision	Recall
0.5319	0.2004	0.5717	0.5211

This decline is indicative of the anticipated trade-off between accuracy and robustness, where the model prioritizes stability under perturbations over maximum precision on clean inputs [15].

The baseline performance remains largely comparable, with only a slight decrease, suggesting that the model's basic detection ability is unaffected by adversarial training.

5.2 Global Robustness Under FGSM Attacks

The adversarially trained model demonstrates substantially improved robustness under FGSM adversarial attacks. As shown in Table 4 and the corresponding metric comparison figures, the degradation of mAP50 and Recall happens more gradually as ϵ increases.

Table 4 Global performance of adversarially trained model under FGSM Attacks

FGSM ϵ	mAP50	mAP50-95	Precision	Recall
0	0.5319	0.2004	0.5717	0.5211
0.005	0.5384	0.2021	0.5577	0.5134
0.01	0.495	0.1784	0.4604	0.5249
0.02	0.3359	0.1236	0.4243	0.3487
0.03	0.269	0.0985	0.415	0.3065
0.05	0.1644	0.0581	0.3176	0.1992
0.1	0.0642	0.0213	0.1975	0.0881

Figure 5 mAP50 comparison between undefended and adversarially trained YOLOv8 models under FGSM attacks

Across all assessed perturbation strengths, recall values remain consistently higher than those of the undefended model, suggesting that the defended model retains a higher percentage of accurate detections. Precision also shows increased stability, indicating that adversarial training does not significantly increase false positives.

These findings demonstrate that adversarial training considerably reduces, but does not completely eliminate, the impact of FGSM attacks, even though performance degradation persists at higher ϵ values.

Figure 7 Recall comparison between undefended and adversarially trained YOLOv8 models under FGSM adversarial perturbations

Figure 6 Precision comparison between undefended and adversarially trained YOLOv8 models for increasing FGSM perturbation strength

5.3 Robustness Against PGD Attacks

To further validate the robustness of the adversarially trained model, the evaluation was extended to include Projected Gradient Descent attacks. PGD is a stronger iterative extension of FGSM. Rather than applying a single gradient step, PGD applies multiple small steps, making it a more challenging adversary. The adversarial example is generated as $x^0 = x$, then iteratively:

$$x^{t+1} = \Pi_{x+S}(x^t + \alpha \text{sign}(\nabla_x L)) \quad \text{Eq 2}$$

... where α is the step size and the projection Π ensures that the perturbation remains bounded within an ϵ -ball around the original input [14].

All PGD experiments were conducted with 15 iterations and an alpha set to $\epsilon/4$. The PGD perturbation levels were selected to match the FGSM evaluation protocol as closely as possible. Table 5 presents the performance of the baseline model under PGD attacks. At $\epsilon=0.005$, the baseline still achieves an mAP50 of 0.4514; performance deteriorates rapidly with increasing perturbation strength. At $\epsilon=0.02$, the perturbation level used in adversarial training mAP50 falls to 0.1586, and Recall drops to 0.1762, compared to 0.255 and 0.2874 under FGSM at the same ϵ . At $\epsilon=0.05$, the detector reaches

near-total failure with mAP50 of 0.0262, and at $\epsilon=0.1$ it becomes entirely non-functional, with mAP50 of 0.0031 and Recall of 0.0077.

Table 5 Baseline model performance under PGD attacks

ϵ	mAP50	mAP50-95	Precision	Recall
0.005	0.4514	0.1626	0.5185	0.4662
0.01	0.3763	0.1283	0.5068	0.3701
0.02	0.1586	0.0543	0.3611	0.1762
0.03	0.0897	0.0315	0.2595	0.1111
0.05	0.0262	0.0080	0.0909	0.0766
0.1	0.0031	0.0015	0.0108	0.0077

Table 6 presents the performance of the adversarially trained model (trained on clean images and images with an FGSM attack) under the same PGD conditions.

The defended model demonstrates substantially improved resilience across the full perturbation range. At $\epsilon=0.005$, mAP50 reaches 0.5104 and Recall 0.5562, marginally exceeding even the clean baseline performance of the undefended model, which suggests that at low perturbation strengths the adversarially trained model has internalized sufficiently robust feature representations to maintain stable detection. At $\epsilon=0.02$, the defended model retains an mAP50 of 0.4217 and a Recall of 0.4521, compared to 0.1586 and 0.1762 for the baseline, a gap that directly reflects the benefit of training at this specific perturbation level. Even at $\epsilon=0.05$, the defended model maintains an mAP50 of 0.2092 and a Recall of 0.2069, while the baseline collapses to 0.0262 and 0.0766, respectively. At $\epsilon=0.1$, both models approach failure, though the defended model retains a marginally higher mAP50 of 0.0273 versus 0.0031 for the baseline.

Table 6 FGSM-trained model performance under PGD attacks

ϵ	mAP50	mAP50-95	Precision	Recall
0.005	0.5104	0.1938	0.5109	0.5562
0.01	0.5061	0.1848	0.5045	0.5364
0.02	0.4217	0.1575	0.4747	0.4521
0.03	0.3429	0.1238	0.4226	0.3563
0.05	0.2092	0.0714	0.3476	0.2069
0.1	0.0273	0.0087	0.0852	0.0690

These results demonstrate that adversarial training on FGSM examples provides meaningful cross-attack generalization, offering partial but significant protection against the stronger PGD attack. The Recall and Precision metrics show the clear distinction between the two models.

5.4 Limitations of the Approach

Despite the encouraging results, several limitations of this study must be acknowledged. First, only one adversarial attack technique (FGSM) was considered for the adversarially trained model. Even though FGSM is a popular baseline attack, stronger and more adaptive attacks could further challenge the model's robustness [16].

Second, only one model architecture and a relatively small dataset were used in the experiments. While this configuration is adequate for demonstrating basic vulnerabilities, overall conclusions would need to be tested across multiple architectures and larger, more varied datasets.

Lastly, adversarial training increases training difficulty and computational cost, and it does not guarantee complete immunity to adversarial attacks. Rather than being a standalone solution, it should be seen as one component of a multi-layered defense strategy [17].

6 Conclusion

This study demonstrates that FGSM attacks can strongly degrade object detection performance, even when the perturbations are small and not visible to humans. The main failure mode is the loss of true detections rather than the creation of false ones. As a result, Recall drops sharply, which makes the model unreliable in practice.

The results also confirm that visual similarity is not a reliable measure of model safety. Images that look unchanged to humans can still cause large errors in detection. This exposes a core weakness of deep neural networks: small input changes can shift decision boundaries and disrupt model behavior.

Adversarial training improves robustness. The trained model keeps higher Recall and mAP values as

attack strength increases. This shows that the model learns more stable and general features. There is a small drop in performance on clean data, but this trade-off leads to better performance under attack. The extended evaluation against PGD attacks further confirms this conclusion. Although the adversarially trained model was not explicitly trained against iterative attacks, it maintains considerably higher detection performance under PGD perturbations than the undefended baseline.

These findings have a direct impact on real-world systems. In safety-critical tasks such as surveillance, autonomous driving, and crowd monitoring, missing a real object is more dangerous than producing a false alarm. Undetected objects can lead to safety risks, system failure, and legal issues.

Overall, the results show that adversarial robustness must be part of model design. Testing only on clean data is not enough. AI systems need to be evaluated under adversarial conditions and trained with defense methods. This is necessary to build reliable and safe computer vision systems.

Conflicts of Interest: The author(s) report there are no competing interests to declare;

Data availability statements: The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author;

The source code, experimental implementation, and obtained results are publicly available on GitHub: [https://github.com/marijanab02/Adversarial AI](https://github.com/marijanab02/Adversarial_AI)

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